

1 **Next generation sequencing of HPV+ and HPV- cancer.**

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7 We performed next generation sequencing of HPV+ and HPV- head and neck cancer to describe primary
8 tumors of viral origin in man at the transcriptome level. HPV+ cancers expressed high levels of the
9 intermediate filament *Nefh*. *Arhgap33* activation was observed in HPV+ cancer. Immune receptor
10 composition was different in HPV+ primary tumors with activation of *Muc16* but silencing of *Ly6g6c*. HPV+
11 cancers were rich in expression of the PML gene. We describe here *Barx2* activation in HPV- cancers.

12 Citations

13 1. Lechner, M., Frampton, G.M., Fenton, T., Feber, A., Palmer, G., Jay, A., Pillay, N., Forster, M.,
14 Cronin, M.T., Lipson, D. and Miller, V.A., 2013. Targeted next-generation sequencing of head and neck
15 squamous cell carcinoma identifies novel genetic alterations in HPV+ and HPV-tumors. *Genome*
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